

Hammouda Pacha and the Role of the Dutch in the Construction of a New Port for Tunis (1794-1808)

René Spitz

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René Spitz has a PhD in social sciences (Leiden University; 2014). He is a former policy officer and diplomate of the Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

1. Introduction

In 1794 Hammouda Pacha, the ruler or *Bey* of Tunis, sent a letter to the Dutch authorities via its consul, asking for technical assistance for the modernisation of the port of Tunis in nearby La Goulette. August Heinrich Frank, a military engineer showed interest and was sent in 1796 with two assistants to Tunis. Frank returned to the Netherlands in 1806; his assistant Humbert stayed behind and completed the works in 1808. The Dutch consul in Tunis, Anthony Nijssen (or Nyssen as written in many documents), was the intermediary between Hammouda Pacha, the Dutch authorities, and the engineers during the course of the port modernisation project.

There are two authors who wrote in detail about the Dutch involvement in the modernisation of the port of la Goulette. The French-Tunisian sociologist and historian Paul Sebag included Colonel August Heinrich Frank's project proposal for the modernisation of the port of La Goulette in his book on large construction works in Tunis at the end of the 18th century. Sebag's focus is on the technical information in Frank's proposal, such as materials, machinery, and manpower. He concludes that at the end of the 18th century, a substantial technical gap existed between 'Barbary' (the name Europeans gave to this region in Northwest Africa) and Europe, because engineers and other specialists came from Europe as well as much of the materials and equipment used. The Dutch historian Gérard van Krieken authored two articles which have been published by the Tunisian scientific magazine *Revue de l'Institut des Belles Lettres Arabes* (IBLA).

The first article, published in 1988, is a detailed description of the project, focusses on the modernisation. The article is based on information from the Dutch National Archive in The Hague. Van Krieken discusses Colonel Frank's project proposal as well as its execution under the supervision of the engineers. He dwells on the problems reported by Consul Nijssen with regards to the payment of the engineers' stay, as well as the behaviour of the colonel, who was a competent technician but socially awkward. The Bey repeatedly raised concerns with the consul about the Netherlands not honouring its commitment to send presents under the peace and navigation treaty with Tunis.

The second article is also based on the Dutch archives, describing the development of bilateral relations between the Netherlands and Tunisia. Besides a summary of the modernisation of the port of La Goulette, the article provides information about members of the Nijssen family, who served as the Netherlands' consul in Tunis for over 150 years. Anthony Nijssen was one of them.

Although Anthony Nijssen's role is mentioned in Van Krieken's articles, the significance of his contribution to the creation of a modern port in La Goulette is not analysed. This article aims at assessing the political importance of the role of Consul Anthony Nijssen in the realisation of the

modernisation of the port of La Goulette. Nijssen's role is assessed in relation to the Bey and his entourage, the Dutch authorities, and the engineers.

The research aims at answering the following main questions: what specific activities of a political nature the Dutch consul Anthony Nijssen performed in facilitating the project and its implementation, and how important was his involvement.

My theoretical framework consists of three interrelated concepts: transactional diplomacy, power, and cultural sensitivity. I will use these concepts in describing the relationship between the Dutch Republic and the Ottoman province or Regency of Tunis. I also use these concepts in assessing the contribution of Consul Nijssen to the Dutch involvement in the modernisation of the port of Tunis.

The concept transactional diplomacy refers to relationships that are not based on common values, but rather 'judged on what they deliver to the country, partnerships, no matter how strong they look early on'.¹ Governments have instruments with which national interests can be fostered. Diplomacy is one of these instruments besides other ones like military and economic power. One way of defining diplomacy is:

'Diplomacy fundamentally consists of a constant assessment of other countries' power potential, perceived vital interests, relationship with other states, in an attempt to maximize one's own country's freedom of action with the ultimate purpose of assuring the achievement of the nation's vital interests, the core of which is survival.'²

The use of force can be an element of power. However, having influence and the ability to project it can also be considered as power.³ The latter implies that diplomacy is a process of communication. Diplomats represent states and perform roles. Their added value consists of their 'presumed experience and their familiarity with the country, its culture, institutions, and key personalities'.⁴ Having cultural sensitivity is an important asset for diplomatic work. Cultural sensitivity can be defined as:

'...having an understanding of another person's set of beliefs or values that is attributed to the person's ethnic or racial background. In addition, an individual must be agreeable to modify their behaviour to accommodate the other person's cultural beliefs'.⁵

This research into Consul Nijssen's role is based on primary as well as secondary sources. Primary sources are the reports sent by Anthony Nijssen to the Dutch authorities as well as the latter's instructions. Nijssen's correspondence with Frank and Humbert provides additional insight not only

¹ Bashirov and Ylmaz, pp. 166-167

² Fendrick, pp.179-180.

³ Tenembaum

⁴ Fendrick, pp. 181-182.

⁵ Study. com. *Cultural Sensitivity | Definition, Importance & Examples*, consulted 12 January 2025,

into the implementation of the project, but also into their personal relationships. Most of these letters are in the national archive in The Hague; additional correspondence is found in the archive of the national museum for antiquities in Leiden. The information is contextualised by comments made by contemporaries, such as consuls living and working in Tunis.

Secondary sources include background studies on the reign of Hammouda Pacha, the relations between European states and Tunis in the 18th century, and the role of European consuls within this context.

2. Anthony Nijssen, consul of the Netherlands

In order to understand Consul Anthony Nijssen's contribution to the Bey's modernisation of the port of Tunis project, I will briefly provide some contextual information about developments in the Netherlands at that time, as well as on the relations between the Dutch Republic and the Regency of Tunis. During the second half of the 18th century, the Netherlands went through a period of economic stagnation and political turmoil. The Dutch Republic was weakened by a series of wars against their more powerful British and French neighbours.⁶ From 1795 until 1813, the Netherlands became a vassal state of France. It managed to secure a quasi-independence as Batavian Republic (1795-1805) and from 1806 until 1810 as Kingdom Holland; however, from 1810 onwards, the Netherlands became fully incorporated into the French Empire. The British reacted by a declaration of war and a blockade.⁷ During this period, Dutch overseas trade was brought to a near standstill. From 1814 onwards, after the defeat of the French army, the Netherlands regained its independence.⁸

The Netherlands and the Ottoman Regency of Tunis had a long-standing peaceful relationship based on peace and navigation treaties signed and renewed since 1622, the last of which was signed in 1760.⁹ The main reason for these treaties was to protect Dutch commercial vessels and their crews against piracy and captivity.¹⁰ As corollary from the treaties, Tunis and the other Ottoman Regencies in Northwest Africa had the right to receive a kind of compensation, or tax, from the Dutch authorities for the Dutch ships sailing along the Maghreb coast. Since the North African rulers preferred to receive this compensation in goods rather than in cash (only), the confusing word 'presents' was used.¹¹ The consuls in North Africa were entrusted by the Dutch government with a wide range of political and commercial responsibilities—duties that, elsewhere, would typically fall to ambassadors. These included concluding treaties and offering gifts, assisting Dutch merchants, negotiating the release of enslaved Dutch sailors, and serving as conduits of information, particularly—but not exclusively—on commercial matters.¹² These consuls were considered by the Dutch authorities as

⁶ Wielenga, pp. 167 and 175.

⁷ NRC, 15-16 March 2025. A peace agreement was signed on 18 October 1799 in Alkmaar (North Holland).

⁸ Britannica, *History of the Netherlands*. The 18th century; The Hague International Centre, *History of the Netherlands*

⁹ Rousseau, pp. 517-526.

¹⁰ Groot, p. 134.

¹¹ Nanninga, p. VIII

¹² Heinsen-Roach, p. 92 and 104

state representatives and received a fixed annual remuneration because of lack of any significant trading communities in these countries that could pay commissions for consular services.¹³ In addition to their regular salary, the consuls received so-called ‘expenditure money’ with which they could pay for small gifts to the local ruler and his ministers.¹⁴ In several cases, these consuls belonged to locally established families with their own business interests, as was the case for those representing the Dutch Republic in Tunis in the 18th and 19th centuries. They had been chosen by their government to become consul because they were well integrated in the local society, thus familiar with the culture and language.¹⁵ This was also the case for members of the Nijssen family.¹⁶

In this context, Anthony Nijssen’s started his consular activities. Anthony Nijssen was the son of Arnout Hendrik Nijssen and Maddalena Gazzo. His parents were Catholics.¹⁷ Arnout Hendrik Nijssen was a Dutch entrepreneur who was appointed consul for the Dutch Republic in Tunis in 1761. Arnout Nijssen died on 13 March 1792 in Tunis.¹⁸ He married in 1754 in Tunis with Maddalena Gazzo, who was the daughter of Doctor Giambattista Gazzo, the consul of Venice in Tunis. Maddalena originated from the island of Tabarka, off the coast of Tunisia. This island had previously been under Genoese control but was occupied by Tunis in 1741.¹⁹ Gazzo was a former slave who had become surgeon at the Bey’s court and, at a later stage, was appointed consul at the Bey’s request.²⁰

Anthony Nijssen was born in 1765 and grew up in Tunis.²¹ He had two brothers: Charles and César²², and he also had three sisters: Marie Therese (1760²³), Antonia (1762), and Jeanne Sibylle (Giovanna Sibilìa) (1767).²⁴ In the letters and documents written by Anthony Nijssen or sent to him, there are no indications that Anthony Nijssen himself was married nor whether he had any children. There were family ties between the Nijssen family and the Soler family, a Spanish family of consuls in Tunis. Jaimy Soler married Antonia and became consul-general and *charge d’affaires* in Tunis after having had a similar position in Tripoli.²⁵

The Nijssen’s family lived in the small European quarter of the *mediena*, the old city, in the consular building itself. This area for foreigners, next to the city gate *Bab al-Bahr* (door to the sea), developed from the 16th century onwards into a Christian or European zone. From the late 16th century onwards,

¹³ Galen Last, p. 59 and 62.

¹⁴ Galen Last, p. 61.

¹⁵ Windler (2015), pp. 345- 352; Windler (2003), p.72

¹⁶ Jerad (2023), p. 2; Jerad (2024), p. 438.

¹⁷ Ghali, 2022, p.18

¹⁸ Schutte, O, pp.372-373.

¹⁹ Leone, pp. 119-120

²⁰ Ghali, 2022, p.13.

²¹ Riggio, pp. 93-124.

²² Schutte, p.372-373; Krieken, p. 238.

²³ Rijksmuseum van Oudheden, consulted 5 May 2025. Frank’s assistant Jean Emile Humbert married in 1801 Anthony’s sister Therese.

²⁴ Ghali, 2022, p.18. Foot note 32.

²⁵ Loth, p. 12. According to Loth was the name of Jaimy Soler’s spouse Angela; Nationaal Archief, nr. 357/A report of 21 January 1799 from Anthony Nijssen to van der Goes, agent for foreign relation in the Hague. J. Soler died in 1798 and left behind his wife and many children.

the French, the English, and the Dutch established their consulates in this area near the sea and the port of La Goulette.²⁶ In the 18th century, more countries—such as the United States, Spain, Denmark, Sweden, and others—had consulates.²⁷ At the time, consulates were mere buildings made available by the Tunisian authorities to house the consuls and their offices, as well as to provide space for their trading nationals and their goods. These buildings were known as *fondouks* (literally: inns) or *caravanserais* and were built around a closed court yard, accessible via a massive, covered door.²⁸ The Dutch consulate initially shared a building with the consul of Britain at *place de la Bourse*, where the Bab al Bahr is situated. The consulate moved to the nearby Rue Zarkoun in the first half of the 19th century. The Dutch consul, like a couple of other consuls, had also a country house outside Tunis. In this more informal setting, compared to the Bey’s court, consuls and high-ranking Tunisian officials also met.²⁹ The consular building could be seen from a distance by the flagpole on its terrasse, with the national flag flying at the top. The entrance of the consulate was always guarded by a few *janissaires*, Turkish soldiers.³⁰

Source: Humbert files, Archive National Museum of Antiquities, Leiden.

²⁶ Calafat, p. 5.

²⁷ Ghali, 2015, p.17-18 ; see in this book footnote 25 and 26 for the original sources.

²⁸ Falgas, p.379 and 384; Calafat, p.12.

²⁹ Krieken (2008) p.277.

³⁰ Frank, p.91

Where and from whom Anthony Nijssen got his education is not known; there were no European schools prior to 1830.³¹ He could express himself in both speech and writing in French and Italian. Anthony also must have had knowledge of Dutch since he sent declarations of annual extraordinary expenses in this language. While Anthony wrote his reports in French to The Hague, he received instructions in Dutch from the Dutch authorities.³² He probably also understood the local Arabic dialect.³³ Hammouda Pacha, the Bey, spoke Arabic and Ottoman Turkish, as well as the Italian dialect, which was the *linguae franca* and used in commercial and diplomatic relations of his time. Italian was the second language at the court; it was used in all official dealings with European and American powers as well as in diplomatic correspondence.³⁴ Ottoman-Turkish was also used in diplomatic correspondence to European states, as is reflected in the letters the Bey sent to the Dutch authorities.³⁵

Anthony Nijssen became young vice-consul in 1780 and worked as a consul for the Netherlands from 1792 until 1810, when the Netherlands was fully occupied by France. He was reinstated as consul by the Dutch authorities in 1814 and held this position until his death in 1825 in Marseille.³⁶ He also served as consul for Tuscany,³⁷ Austria,³⁸ the Republic of Ragusa or Dubrovnik,³⁹ as well as, at the request of the Bey, a commercial agent for Russia.⁴⁰ Nijssen authored an article with observations on life in Tunis,⁴¹ and he is mentioned in letters and reports of contemporaries at European consulates in Tunis, such as the French former first interpreter Alphonse Rousseau, the French consul Devoize, the Spanish *chargé d'affaires* Arnoldo Soler, the Danish vice-consul Louis Joseph Hameken, and the British consul Perkins Magra.

The consulate itself was a family business: besides Anthony, his brothers Charles and César also worked there. Then Henri, son of César, was chancellor of the consulate since 1791, who acted as secretary for his uncle Anthony.⁴² César was appointed in June 1794 as unpaid chancellor. He became consul in October 1825 after the death of Anthony Nijssen. Charles (Carel) Nijssen and second son of

³¹ Salah, p.5.

³² Nationaal Archief, 1.02. 21. 01, nr.7; For example: Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Missive Van der Goes Secretary of Foreign Affairs to consul Nijssen, 28 December 1804.*

³³ Galen Last, pp. 157-158. His brother Charles Nijssen applied successfully for the position of consul-general in Tanger (Morocco). He had been vice-consul until 1810 in Tunis. He was of the opinion that he qualified for this position since he 'knew the Barbarian languages as well as how to deal with Issues in Barbary'.

³⁴ Triulzi, p. 161.

³⁵ Nationaal Archief, 1.01.02, inventory number 6996 (1795), attachment to *report Nijssen to High and Mighty Lords of 10 December 1794*; Nationaal Archief; nr. 357/A, *Letter of Hammouda Bey to the Mighty Lords who now govern the Batavian Commonwealth, translated from Turkish, 29 September 1802 (Jumada althani, 1217)*, in which he refers to the visit of vice-admiral De Winter, the friendship between the two nations and requests to ship as soon as possible the agreed items to Tunis.

³⁶ Schutte, O. pp.372-373; Galen Last, p. 701.

³⁷ Leone, p.119.

³⁸ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 8 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to Citizen van Leijden, Secretary of the National Assembly to the Foreign Affairs Committee*; Fendri, p.426 footnote 52. His father A.H. Nijssen represented Austria in Tunis since 1783,

³⁹ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 8 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to Citizen van Leijden, Secretary of the National Assembly to the Foreign Affairs Committee*; Duke University. *Perkins Magra papers.*

⁴⁰ Duke University. *Perkins Magra papers.*

⁴¹ See Monchicourt.

⁴² Galen Last, pp. 703-704.

Arnout Nijssen, was vice-consul in Tunis from 1804 until 1810.⁴³ While the Dutch consul and his vice-consul received an annual remuneration, other sources of income appeared to be limited. Although the Dutch authorities permitted the Dutch consul to engage in commerce,⁴⁴ the profits made appeared to be few. Anthony's father mentioned in a letter to the Dutch authorities in 1788 that no earnings could be made in Tunis, and that he and his extended family had to live off the dwindling possessions of his wife.⁴⁵

Anthony Nijssen, in his role as consul or agent⁴⁶ for various states, had frequent contacts with the Bey and his ministers on a range of issues, such as the release of European captives,⁴⁷ the liberation of captured commercial ships along with their cargo and crew, the issuance of passports to ships of the Regency, and the bilateral treaties on peace and navigation.⁴⁸

Source: National Archive Tunis, part of a joint proposal of consuls in Tunis to the Bey via his minister Keeper of the Seal of 23 October 1798 for the release of the enslaved citizens, of the island of San Pietro (Sardinia), by Tunisian corsairs.

Depending on the political relations between European countries and the nature of the dispute, Anthony Nijssen was either regarded by other consuls as a trustworthy friend and partner,⁴⁹ or as an

⁴³ Schutte, p.373.

⁴⁴ Nyssen, p.15

⁴⁵ Nationaal Archief, B.102.21.01, nr. 6, Report of Arnout Hendrik Nijssen to the Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 10 June 1788.

⁴⁶ Hafedh, p.11. Nijssen represented French interests when its consulate was closed due to the war between the Ottoman empire and France as a consequence of Napoleon's incursion in Egypt (1798-1801).

⁴⁷ Chenoufi, p. 264; Foti and Blando, p. 869; Leone, p. 119.

⁴⁸ Foti and Blando, p. 869.

⁴⁹ Plantet, 762, report of Devoize to Talleyrand, 29 September 1800.

opponent⁵⁰ and/or schemer.⁵¹ All of them noted that Anthony had good relations with the Bey and his administration. However, some of them suggested that Nijssen, due to debts to the Bey and influential Tunisians, always worked in the interest of the Bey.⁵² In a letter dated 20 August 1801 to Tinne—a Dutch government official and friend of the Nijssen’s family—Anthony noted that the Bey and the all-powerful minister Youssuf Koggia 'go so far as to confide in me their most intimate confidences' ... 'This pleasant and honourable situation has many times put me in the position of rendering signal services to this Prince and to friends, without compromising myself, as the government of our Republic may have been informed without me'.⁵³

3. A new port for Tunis

The city of Tunis is separated from the sea by a shallow marsh. During the reign of Hussein bin Ali, the first Bey of the Husaynid dynasty, a small port was dug at La Goulette (Halq al-Wadi in Arabic).

Source: *Plan des forts et canal de La Goulette, 1764* by Nicolas Bellin, *Centre d'Etudes Maghrébines, Tunis*.

⁵⁰ Plantet. 626, *report of Herculaïs to Delacroix*, annex 1, 19 February 1797;

⁵¹ Duke University. *Perkins Magra papers*; Plantet, 978, *Billon au Duc de Bassano*, 31 May 1812. Duc de Bassano was a diplomat and secretary of state; Foti and Blando, p. 869.

⁵² Duke University. *Perkins Magra papers*; Plantet, 978, *Billon au Duc de Bassano*, 31 May 1812; Chenoufi, *Texte fait à Tunis, le 12 mars 1817*, pp.267-270.

⁵³ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Letter of Anthony Nijssen to B. Tinne of 20 August 1801*, pp. 293-294.

Small boats began to pass through what appeared to be a canal between the capital and its port in Halq al-Wadi (the canal's throat⁵⁴). This canal was so narrow that it did not allow even a small sailing ship to pass through it.⁵⁵

Based on several sources, it can be concluded that the Bey had both commercial and military reasons for his decision to modernise the port of La Goulette. A major reason was to facilitate the transport of goods from the port to Tunis.⁵⁶ Another reason was to protect the port and the mouth of the canal from northeast and southeast winds⁵⁷, as well as safeguard Tunis from foreign intruders.⁵⁸

Source: Portrait of Hammouda Pacha, Institut Supérieur d'Histoire Contemporaine de la Tunisie, La Manouba, Tunis.

The Bey actively sought foreign expertise and support for his modernisation project. He approached allied countries with this request. While it is not certain, it is quite possible that before sending official requests, the Bey and/or his trusted advisers discussed the issue of modernisation with several consuls. The French special representative Herculaïs informed the French authorities in 1795 that he had

⁵⁴ Malouch, p.1.

⁵⁵ Al Imaam, p.234

⁵⁶ Plantet. *Letters of consul Devoize to Talleyrand* 671 of 15 May 1798.

⁵⁷ Krieken (1988), p.222 -223.

⁵⁸ Rousseau, pp.197-215. In the first years after his succession to the throne, Hammouda had to deal with a war with the Republic of Venice. The Venetian bombardments severely damaged the fortifications of La Goulette;

received a letter from the minister, on behalf the Bey, in which it was mentioned that Tunis had a large project that could be beneficial for both Powers.⁵⁹

Hammouda Pacha also approached the Dutch Republic with a similar request. In 1794, he wrote a letter to the Dutch authorities requesting an engineer, accompanied by two assistants, to supervise the modernisation of the port in Tunis. The letter was sent by Consul Anthony Nijssen as an annex to his report of 10 December 1794. Anthony had expressed some doubts to the Bey about the idea, given that the engineer would have to travel to a distant country with a different language. However, the Bey replied:

‘I’m not asking for a man to build fortifications. I am not asking for a man to come at the expense of their High Powers, but I am asking for a skilful master engineer to build a port that will facilitate the trade of my country, that will make the ships of friendly nations safe... I have too often been deceived by the French, who have made me spend a great deal of money without teaching me the basics of the art... I know, despite what you will tell me, that the best masters in this art are in Holland. You people, he added, you created your country in the middle of the water, and human judgement can barely conceive this masterpiece. I want a master engineer from Holland because all my courtiers have assured me that there are none more skilful in the world to execute this work.’⁶⁰

The Bey’s request arrived in the Dutch Republic during a time of significant political and military turmoil in the Netherlands. The Batavian Republic was proclaimed on 20 January 1795. Immediately afterwards, William V, the Stadtholder-the highest political authority-fled to England. Anthony had to take notice of these profound and revolutionary political changes in the Netherlands, as well as how to address his superiors: from ‘High and Mighty Lords’ to ‘Citizen Representatives’.⁶¹

The authorities of the Batavian Republic decided positively on the Bey’s request, forwarded by Consul Nijssen, in April 1795, and published a vacancy in Dutch newspapers.⁶² The military engineer Colonel Frank applied and was sent to Tunis in 1796. His two assistants were Captains Frank (his son Christian Ferdinand) and Jean Emile Humbert. They travelled, accompanied by Anthony’s brother Charles overland to Marseille, where they boarded a ship to Tunis. They travelled overland because, at that time, the Netherlands and Great Britain were at war. The journey to Tunis, where the engineers arrived on 17 March 1796, was paid for by the Dutch authorities, while the Bey would cover their stay.⁶³

⁵⁹ Plantet, nr. 542, 30 July 1795.

⁶⁰ Nationaal Archief, Staten-Generaal, 1.01.02, 6996 (1795), *Report of Nijssen of 10 December 1794 to High and Mighty lords* with attached letter of the Bey.

⁶¹ Nationaal Archief. *Bataafse revolutie (1795)*, consulted 31 March 2025.

⁶² Goetgevonden, Resolutie States-General of 9 April 1795.

⁶³ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report Nijssen of 5 April 1796 to High and Mighty lords*.

Van Krieken provides the following information about the three officers. August Heinrich Frank was 55 years old at the start of his mission in Tunis. He was born in Dresden, Germany. In 1784, he became a captain engineer in the Dutch military. His son, Christian Ferdinand, was born in 1772, and his fellow student, Jean Emile Humbert, was born in 1771 in The Hague, as son of a Dutch artistic painter. Before leaving for Tunis, August Frank was promoted to lieutenant colonel, and his two assistants were promoted to lieutenant captain.⁶⁴

What exactly motivated Frank to apply for the vacancy published by the Batavian Republic is not known. Perhaps Frank hoped to be well paid for his expertise by the Bey, which would enable him to retire without financial concerns. Reportedly, Humbert was motivated to go to Tunis because he did not want to serve in the Batavian army.⁶⁵ They arrived in Tunis on 17 March 1796 after a seven-day boat trip. The Bey was very pleased with the arrival of the colonel and his team, as well as with a letter of friendship of the Dutch Batavian authorities. The Bey even served them coffee during Ramadan, noted Nijssen. However, Anthony Nijssen soon received confidential information after this first meeting information that the Bey might request the Dutch authorities to cover the expenses of Frank and his assistants' stay, much like the French did for their engineers and workers in Tunis. He warned the Dutch authorities for this possibility in the report.⁶⁶ Moreover, the Bey continued to complain about the delay in sending gifts by the Dutch authorities.⁶⁷

During the first five months after their arrival, the engineers prepared detailed plans for three ports: La Goulette, Portefarine, and Bizerte. However, after reception of these plans, the Bey remained silent. Finally, after seven months, the Bey requested that the engineers renovate the canal of La Goulette, a much more limited project than the original request.⁶⁸ Later, this request was expanded to include the construction of two docks in La Goulette: one for the navy and one for commercial ships.

Frank developed a new plan consisting of three elements: the protection of the mouth of the channel from winds by two piers, the deepening of the existing canal, and the creation of two docks. Frank's plan, with a quotation dated 17 August 1796, has been published by Paul Sebag.⁶⁹ Gérard van Krieken summarised the plan as follows:

'Engineer Frank's plan [...] aims to develop two docks on the edge of the lake in eight years: one, located to the south of the existing canal, reserved for the navy and the other, located to

⁶⁴ Krieken (2008), p.244. Frank was appointed by the States-General (by resolution of 27 November 1795) to build a port in Tunis, following a request from the Bey of Tunis; Plantet. *Correspondances des Beys et des consuls. Letters of consul Devoize to Talleyrand* 671 of 15 May 1798. Plantet mentions Homberg as brother-in-law of Anthony Nijssen. This is incorrect; it should be Humbert.

⁶⁵ Begraafplaats Groenesteeg.

⁶⁶ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report Nijssen of 5 April 1796 to High and Mighty lords*

⁶⁷ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report Nijssen of 21 February 1797 to citizen representatives.*

⁶⁸ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report Nijssen nr. 2, 21 February 1797 from consul Anthony Nijssen to Citizen representatives in the Hague.*

⁶⁹ Sebag, p.2

the north, for merchant ships. Each dock, with an area of 188 m by 133 m, could accommodate up to fifty ships arriving via the 700 m long canal, but the depth would have to be increased to 4.60 m. The mouth of this canal, which is to face south, will be protected from the northeast and southeast winds by two piers. It is also planned that the spoil from the digging of the canal will be brought around the basins, so that houses and stores can be built there. All of these works require, among other things: 74,000 m³ of stones that ten pontoons could bring from the quarry of Jebel al-Manar, located in Sidi Bou Said; 15,000 m³ of pozzolan for cement; 11,500 m³ of quicklime; approximately 18,000 planks and 9,300 piles. The project also specifies the number of workers Frank will need: 180 men to work in the quarry, 80 men to transport the stones to La Goulette. Using ten pontoons, they could complete this transport in 822 trips or 2,466 days. In La Goulette itself, digging the canal and clearing the earth requires 300 "steady and well-directed" men, 300 wheelbarrows, and 100 horse-drawn carts. The construction of the revetments would provide work for 200 men, including 32 masons, 20 carpenters, and 30 to 40 experienced stonemasons. It is even proposed that by adopting piecework wages, the duration of the work could be limited to six years.⁷⁰

Frank also created very important military defence structures, the most significant of which was fortifying the entrance of the canal from la Goulette side by installing a fence made of huge stakes on both sides of the canal. The strong stone barricades at certain points at the entrance to the canal were not visible except to the competent officials of the port of La Goulette. In the event of an attack on these barricades, there was a serious risk of being exposed to the bombardments with large-calibre canons from the newly constructed towers. Father Caroni, a visitor to Tunis, described in 1804 the importance and strength of these constructions, stating that from that day on, an aggressor, no matter how strong, would not break through these formidable barriers.⁷¹

Due to technical challenges, such as the construction of a lock to protect the canal from silting up, and delays in receiving the needed materials, it took Frank nine years to complete most of the work. For financial reasons, the Bey decided to construct only one dock. After Frank returned to the Netherlands in early 1806, Jean Emile Humbert remained.⁷² Humbert completed the final pier of the port of La Goulette and reinforced fortifications in Tunis. In addition to his engineering work, Humbert conducted important archaeological excavations in Carthage. Nijssen highlighted in a letter to the Dutch Minister of Foreign Affairs in March 1809 the significant contribution of Humbert's activities to the maintenance of good relations between the Bey and the Netherlands.⁷³

⁷⁰ Krieken (2008), pp 245-246.

⁷¹ Al Imaam, p. 237.

⁷² Krieken (2008), p. 249.

⁷³ Halbertsma, pp.73-74; Nationaal Archief nr. 357, *Report of 23 March 1809 of consul Anthony Nijssen to Roëll, the minister of Foreign Affairs to the King of Holland.* pp. 162-165.

Source: Portrait of Jean Emile Humbert, National Museum of Antiquities, Leiden, The Netherlands.

The Bey and his administration had to arrange for all the materials and workers. Many of the materials had to be imported, which could cause delays. The Bey instructed the purchase of necessary materials in several European ports and also requested them from other nations, such as Sweden, Denmark, and the United States: wood, sheet piles, piles, and pozzolana from Italy.⁷⁴ The Bey also needed specialised equipment, such as pontons, which he requested from France.⁷⁵ In Portefarine, pontons and other equipment were made.⁷⁶

The workers were often enslaved Europeans, many of Italian origin, who were tasked with the hard labour. Some were much-needed specialist, like carpenters. The three engineers sent by the Netherlands oversaw the works. Frank chose Cubisol, a free French citizen and constructor who worked for the Bey at his arsenal in Portefarine, as his right-hand man. Cubisol's presence was so crucial for Frank that he even threatened to leave for the Netherlands if the Bey posted him elsewhere. Nijssen felt obliged to pay Cubisol from his own pocket for ten years to ensure that he would continue working for Frank.⁷⁷

4. Consul Nijssen's political challenges

Consul Nijssen had to manage issues of political nature prior to and during implementation of the port project. The main issue was to convince the Bey of the political will of the Dutch authorities to maintain peaceful relations even though the latter were not sending the promised presents. The intrigues by the French representative aimed at preventing Dutch involvement in the modernisation of the port as well as discrediting Nijssen was another political challenge. The wish of the Bey that the Dutch authorities financed the stay of the engineers in Tunis was a political as well as a practical

⁷⁴ Pozzolana is hydraulic cement made of materials of volcanic origin. <https://www.britannica.com/technology/pozzolana>

⁷⁵ Plantet. *Letters of consul Devoize to Talleyrand* 671 of 15 May 1798 and 706 of 7 January 1799.

⁷⁶ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *letter 5 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to The Foreign Affairs Committee of the National Assembly representing the Batavian People.*

⁷⁷ Nationaal Archief nr. 357, *Report of 7 January 1809 of vice-consul Charles Nijssen to Minister of Foreign Affairs*, pp. 145-147.

problem. Finally, Nijssen had to cope with the possible political consequences of colonel Frank's wish to leave Tunis before having completed the work.

The issue of the promised presents

Between 1794 and 1815, the Dutch authorities were unable to fulfil their obligations under the peace and navigation treaty. The primary reasons were the ongoing war, the British blockade of Dutch ports, and financial difficulties faced by the Dutch state. From the outset of his tenure as consul, Anthony was continuously pressured by Hammouda Pacha and his minister, Youssuf Koggia - the Keeper of the Seal- to take action to ensure the arrival of the promised presents. Only in August 1815, a year after Hammouda's death, did a Dutch naval squadron arrive in Tunis with presents.⁷⁸

Lacking the backing by a powerful Dutch naval force, Anthony tried by other means to preserve harmonious relations with the Bey and his entourage. He explained the reasons for the delay in delivering the promised presents and shared 'confidential information' with the Bey. He offered small gifts to the Bey and to influential individuals who could advocate on his behalf or act in his favour. The Dutch-English war and the blockade of Dutch ports provided, at least temporarily, an excuse for the delay in sending the promised presents. When Anthony informed the Bey of the secret decision made by the National Assembly of the Batavian Republic of 19 June 1796 to declare war against Britain, it was well received. Anthony noted that the Bey:

'...forgot all resentment against me, cancelled the claims that he was about to form at the instigation of his favourite minister the Keeper of the Seal because of the delay in the delivery of the presents. He was very convinced by the speech that I gave him on this subject and assured me again of all his esteem and his friendship for the Republic'.⁷⁹

The positive decision of the Dutch authorities on the request of Hammouda Pacha to send an engineer with two assistants in 1796 to Tunis, as well as the good work delivered by them, positively affected the Dutch-Tunisian relations.⁸⁰ While Nijssen explicitly reported to the Dutch authorities that he had no previous knowledge of the request made by the Bey, he might have had interest in suggesting the idea to the Bey, or his advisor, to solicit Dutch technical support. After all, a positive reply by the Dutch would help to reduce pressure on him and/or the distrust about his role regarding the delayed presents. However, shortly after the arrival of the engineers, Hammouda Pacha resumed his pressure on Consul Nijssen to deliver the promised Dutch presents.

Anthony regularly provided detailed reports on the arrival of shipments of presents from other countries. For example, in his report of 21 February 1797, he informs the Dutch authorities Denmark,

⁷⁸ Krieken (1988), p. 241

⁷⁹ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 8 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to Citizen van Leijden, Secretary of the National Assembly to the Foreign Affairs Committee*

⁸⁰ Nationaal Archief Den Haag nr. 357/A, *Report 5 April 1796 from consul Anthony Nijssen to High and Mighty Lords in the Hague; letter nr. 2, 21 February 1797 from consul Anthony Nijssen to Citizen representatives in the Hague.*

Spain, and France gave considerable presents to the Bey in the past eight months, and that other countries made promises to do the same. In a report dated 8 November 1797 to the Foreign Affairs Commission of the National Assembly of the Batavian Republic, Nijssen noted that, while other countries sent presents and gifts annually or biennially, the Netherlands had given nothing since 1786. Anthony expressed concern about the potential consequences of any further delay.⁸¹

When finally on 8 October 1802 a Dutch naval squadron arrived in Tunis, Anthony Nijssen felt a great sense of relief. The peace agreement of March 1802 between France and Britain, which lasted only a little more than one year, made it possible for the Dutch authorities to show their interest in maintaining peaceful relations with Tunis and other North African states. Dutch Vice Admiral J.W. de Winter⁸² was sent for this reason by the government to Algiers, Tunis and Tripoli on a mission with three warships. However, he did not have the presents the Bey expected. Nevertheless, the Bey welcomed de Winter in a notably positive atmosphere, despite the prolonged absence of senior Dutch representatives.⁸³ However, following the return of the Dutch squadron to the Batavian Republic, the Dutch authorities remained silent. As a result, the Bey and his minister, the Keeper of the Seal, renewed their pressure on Anthony to ensure the delivery of the promised presents. Anthony's situation became even more difficult when the Bey was informed by the Pacha in Tripoli that he had received the agreed presents from the Netherlands, despite the ongoing blockade of Dutch ports. In response, the Bey decided to ask British Admiral Horatio Nelson to facilitate the transport of the Dutch presents by issuing a *laissez-passer* for a Dutch or neutral ship.⁸⁴ However, the British authorities refused to issue such a document, as part of the cargo included ammunition. Dutch State Secretary Van der Goes instructed Nijssen to inform the Bey that the sole reason for the delay in sending the presents was the war.⁸⁵

While anxiously awaiting the arrival of the promised Dutch presents under the peace and navigation treaty, Anthony Nijssen spent many years using his official expenditure funds to maintain good relations with the Bey and key figures as well as with authorities whom Colonel Frank may have offended through his rude behaviour. He purchased and offered 'small gifts' such as silver-plated guns and pistols, furniture, gold watches, snuff boxes lined with pearls, rings, telescopes, and other items.⁸⁶

French intrigues

⁸¹ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Letter nr. 2, 21 February 1797 from consul Anthony Nijssen to Citizen representatives in the Hague*; Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report Nijssen of 8 November 1797 to the Foreign Affairs Commission of the National Assembly*.

⁸² For information about Vice admiral de Winter's career, see Wikipedia, 1911 Encyclopaedia Britannica.

⁸³ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Letter of 18 December 1802 from consul Nijssen to Citizen van Leijden, Secretary of the National Assembly to the Foreign Affairs Committee*

⁸⁴ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 6 February 1804 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*.

⁸⁵ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Missive of 28 December 1804 from Van der Goes, State Secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs to consul Nijssen*.

⁸⁶ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 21 August 1803 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*; Nationaal Archief nr. 357, *Letter of 11 September 1806 of Charles Nijssen, vice-consul in Algiers to Van der Goes, State Secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*

After Engineer Frank submitted his port construction plans to the Bey in 1796, several months passed before a response was received. In the meantime, Anthony sought an audience with the Minister the Keeper of the Seal, the Bey's trusted confidant. According to the Minister, the Bey hesitated due to concerns about the duration of the project and the costs involved. However, Anthony soon learned of intrigues orchestrated by Louis Alexandre d'Allois d'Herculais, the special French envoy of the Republican National Convention to the Barbarian states. Herculais had reportedly suggested to the Bey that the port works could be completed within six months and at significantly lower costs. Anthony protested, insisting that no experienced engineer could accomplish the project in less time or at a lower cost than Frank had proposed.⁸⁷ As previously mentioned, the Bey had approached the French for assistance in implementing the project. Nevertheless, he ultimately appeared convinced by the quality of the Dutch proposal and gave Frank permission to begin the work.

Meanwhile, French opponents of Nijssen attempted—unsuccessfully—to discredit him in the eyes of the Dutch authorities. In 1795, they accused him of anti-French behaviour. However, Anthony was able to refute these allegations by referring to a statement from Devoize, the French consul in Tunis, affirming that his relations with the French were excellent.⁸⁸ Despite this, Herculais considered Anthony Nijssen an enemy of revolutionary France and sought in vain to have him removed.⁸⁹

The payment of the engineers

In his letter to the Dutch authorities, in which he requested the services of an experienced engineer, the Bey had indicated that he would cover all costs incurred during the engineer's stay. However, his minister, the Keeper of the Seal, treated the subsistence allowance for Colonel Frank as an advance to be repaid by the Dutch authorities. Anthony pointed out that other European states covered the costs of their specialists and workers sent to Tunis.⁹⁰ Furthermore, these countries regularly delivered presents as part of their peace and navigation treaties, often arriving with a naval squadron to reinforce their presence. Fully aware that the Batavian Republic could not demonstrate naval strength due to the ongoing war with Britain, Anthony advised to the Dutch authorities to adopt a low profile and to refrain from making any comments regarding the Bey's decision not to pay the subsistence allowance for the Dutch engineers. At the very least:

‘...until it is close to the measures appropriate to tame them [Bey and favourite minister/ RS]. It is appropriate to manage the latter [favourite minister/RS] to preserve good harmony and to avoid that he capriciously forms some request, no matter what nature it may be’.⁹¹

⁸⁷ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report Nijssen nr. 2, 21 February 1797 from consul Anthony Nijssen to Citizen representatives in the Hague*.

⁸⁸ Goetgevonden, Staten-Generaal, *resolutie 3863*, 1795, juli-december, 7 september 1795; Nationaal Archief 1.02.21.01, nr. 13, *brief Philippe Frederic Tinne aan Anthony Nijssen van 8 september 1795*.

⁸⁹ Plantet, *Letter of Herculais to Delacroix, nr. 626 of 19 February 1797*.

⁹⁰ Nationaal Archief Den Haag nr. 357/A, *report of Nijssen to High and Mighty Lord of 5 April 1796*.

⁹¹ Nationaal Archief Den Haag nr. 357/A, *Report of 8 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to Citizen van Leijden, Secretary of the National Assembly to the Foreign Affairs Committee*

An extract from the register of decrees minutes of the Dutch National Assembly dated 19 June 1797 reveals that Anthony Nijssen had proposed a practical solution to the issue of delayed presents, which was subsequently embraced by the Assembly. Acknowledging that sending the promised presents was not a priority due to the strained financial situation of the Batavian Republic, the Assembly agreed that it was in the state's interest to demonstrate flexibility. Nijssen had suggested that reimbursing the Bey for the daily subsistence allowance paid to the Dutch engineers would be significantly less costly than delivering the long-overdue presents. The Assembly accepted his proposal and agreed to refund the Bey for the expenses related to Colonel Frank's upkeep.⁹² In his report to the Assembly, Nijssen emphasised that the payment of the subsistence allowance was a matter of minor expense when weighed against the broader commercial and maritime interests of the Republic—particularly in relation to an Ottoman Regency which, at the time, possessed the largest corsair fleet among the Barbarian states. He further highlighted the high costs other nations faced, citing the example of the King of Naples, who paid 120,000 hard piastres and released 180 Turkish soldiers enslaved in Naples in exchange for the release of a captured Neapolitan warship and its crew.⁹³

By May 1805, in a state of despair, Anthony wrote to Vice-Admiral de Winter, describing the miserable situation in which he and his family found themselves. The Bey had ceased making the advances for Frank's daily allowance, forcing Anthony to cover the expenses from his own funds, as he had never informed Frank that the Bey considered the payments a loan to be reimbursed by the Dutch authorities. De Winter subsequently wrote to Schimmelpenninck, the Grand Pensionary, invoking the obligations of the peace and navigation treaty and the long-term interests of Dutch commerce, 'which we hope one day will revive'. He described Nijssen as 'this brave, but unhappy and forgotten official working in the Barbarian states for the interest of the Nation'.⁹⁴ In 1806, the Dutch finally acted, transferring approximately 200,000 francs to Nijssen via the Dutch consul in Livorno, enabling him to repay the advance received from the Bey.⁹⁵

Colonel Franks's wish for an early leave

As early as 1797, Engineer Colonel Frank informed Anthony that he intended to leave the following May, citing fears of the plague, the intense summer heat, and concerns that the Bey would not reward him as he deserved. However, as Nijssen reported to the Dutch authorities, the Bey consistently expressed respect for the colonel and repeatedly assured that he would be generously compensated.

⁹² Nationaal Archief Den Haag. B. 2.1. 08; nr. 357/A, annex to report *Nijssen of 19 June 1797*.

⁹³ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report from consul Nijssen to the National Assembly of 21 February 1797*.

⁹⁴ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A. *Letter of 20 May 1805 from Nijssen to Vice-admiral de Winter; Letter of 30 July 1805 from Vice-admiral de Winter to Grand Pensionary Schimmelpenninck*.

⁹⁵ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 18 January 1806 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*; Krieken (2008), p.250.

Nijssen requested an urgent reply, noting that Colonel Frank would be more moderate and reasonable without his young son.⁹⁶ In response, the Dutch ministry of Foreign Affairs wrote to Frank in April 1798, referencing the agreement of 11 November 1795. The letter stated that should he return early, he would forfeit his title and would be required to repay his travel allowance, as well as the allowance for his wife, who had remained in the Netherlands.⁹⁷ Frank ultimately decided to continue his work, although he repeatedly expressed his desire to return to the Netherlands to both the Dutch and Tunisian authorities.⁹⁸

Despite all the challenges, the work under the supervision of Colonel Frank progressed. On 22 November 1803, the Bey visited La Goulette to inspect the lock completed by Frank and Nijssen reported that:

‘He was so satisfied with the beauty, the precision and the utility of this work which illustrates his reign, that he gave a thousand sequins. On this same day, the above -mentioned engineer formally renounced any idea to repatriate and promised to complete the port head and the pier that he started, and which form the mouth of the canal and the port of La Goulette built by him with so much success. The Bey on his side promised not to demand anything from the colonel after this work, at the end of which he can repatriate’. [...] ‘To accelerate it as much, rather, His Excellency the Bey has promised by an act that goes to all chancelleries, to give freedom without payment of the approximately eighty Neapolitan slaves employed in these work under the orders and the management of the above colonel.’⁹⁹

Finally, at the beginning of 1806, the Bey agreed to the departure of Colonel Frank and his son, after receiving confirmation of the Dutch authorities’ commitment to fulfil their obligations under the peace and navigation treaty.¹⁰⁰ Anthony considered this permission a sign of the Beys friendship towards the Netherlands and a success of his diplomacy. The Bey insisted that Captain Engineer Humbert should continue with the work of Frank. The Bey himself would pay for the Humbert’s stay.¹⁰¹ Much to Nijssen’s surprise, the Bey also agreed to the departure of four enslaved persons. These individuals had been assigned to Colonel Frank since the beginning of his work at La Goulette. The Bey also

⁹⁶ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 8 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to The Foreign Affairs Committee of the National Assembly representing the Batavian People*; Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 8 November 1797 from consul Nijssen to Citizen van Leijden, Secretary of the National Assembly to the Foreign Affairs Committee*.

⁹⁷ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Letter of 29 April 1798 from Agent of Foreign Affairs to colonel Frank*, p. 141.

⁹⁸ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Letter of Hammouda Pacha to the Dutch authorities of 17 March 1799*. In this letter in Italian, written by the Minister and Keeper of the Seal on behalf of Hammouda Pacha, the Bey expressed his dissatisfaction with Frank’s repeated requests for permission to return. While reaffirming his friendship with the Netherlands, Hammouda emphasised that he would be extremely displeased if he were left with a half-finished – and therefore useless – port, a project that had already cost him a lot.

⁹⁹ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 6 February 1804 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*.

¹⁰⁰ Nationaal Archief nr. 357/A, *Report of 18 January 1806 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*; Nationaal Archief, B 1.02.21.01, *Letter of 14 January 1806 from Anthony Nijssen to Frank*.

¹⁰¹ Nationaal Archief nr. 357, *Report of 8 February 1806 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs*.

provided a travel allowance to Frank and his son. Nijssen noted that the outcome of these negotiations provoked some envy and jealousy among his colleagues.¹⁰²

5. Concluding remarks

The peace and navigation treaty between the Dutch Republic and the Regency of Tunis was the outcome of transactional diplomacy. However, sending the promised presents to the Bey was not a priority for the Dutch authorities due to the war with Britain, the blockage of the ports, and financial difficulties. Hammouda Pacha had clear commercial and security reasons to modernise the port of La Goulette. Information about the quality of Dutch hydraulic engineering appears to have motivated the Bey to send a request to The Hague for Dutch engineers. The Dutch authorities regarded the dispatch of the engineers and covering the cost of their stay in Tunis, as a way to ensure continued peace within the framework of a transactional relationship.

Consul Nijssen had to navigate a number of potential political obstacles relating to the Dutch role in the modernisation of the port of Tunis. Nijssen's personal relationships with his Tunisian counterparts as well as his diplomatic skills and cultural sensitivity, were of major importance to the successful progress of Dutch involvement in the modernisation of the port of La Goulette. This involvement contributed continuation of peaceful relations between the two countries.

¹⁰² Nationaal Archief nr. 357, *Report of 19 April 1806 from consul Nijssen to Van der Goes, state secretary of the department of Foreign Affairs.*

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